

Research Article

Homology Modeling and Structural Assessment of CuNiR of *Pseudomonas Chlororaphis* Subsp. *Aureofaciens* Nirk

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Abstract: The *Nirk* gene encoding the copper containing nitrite reductase (CuNiR) is essential for the conversion of nitrite to nitric oxide and considered the key step in the denitrification process. In spite of opening wide scope of research by homology modeling, little is known about molecular model of *Pseudomonas chlororaphis* subsp. *aureofaciens* CuNiR. Therefore, we intended to predict its structure and structural properties by using various bioinformatics tools. The selected protein is stable, weakly acidic, high temperature sensitive and also contains disordered regions. Three common residues namely Ser2, Pro106 and Ser305 were found as the DNA and RNA binding site in the protein molecule which can be upcoming research prospect. The protein model was predicted by modeler 9v14 program and checked by PDBsum, Verify3D, ProSA, and QMEAN server and ensured the good quality of the model. The predicted model was checked by PROCHECK and showed that 99.0% of the amino acid residues were in favored and allowed region of Ramachandran plot. The predicted protein model contains Cu as ligand and the residue Cys154 is involved in the binding of this ligand. The protein showed the copper ion binding and NO-forming activity as the molecular function with significant score which confirms its actual function. This study provides an evaluated protein model and the structural information of it that will be helpful for further research on the denitrification mechanism of the selected species in the wet laboratory.

INTRODUCTION

Denitrification is an important phase of the nitrogen cycle and is regulated by different enzymes namely nitrate reductase, nitrite reductase, nitric oxide reductase, and nitrous oxide reductase [1]. Denitrifying bacteria are the microorganisms that possess these enzymes as known as denitrifiers [2]. The gaseous end products N_2 , N_2O and NO are released concomitantly in this process [3]. The denitrifying ability may be an advantage because nitrate acts as a substitute terminal electron acceptor in place of oxygen and facilitates respiration in anoxic condition [4]. Denitrification is responsible for the release of fixed nitrogen into the atmosphere in form of N_2 in the environment [5]. This process has also great impact on environment such as global warming [6], ozone layer destruction [7], and fertilizer loss from agricultural soil [8]. Mosier *et al.* [9] reported that denitrification processes in soils are a major source of atmospheric nitrous oxide (N_2O) and soils contribute approximately 57% of the global emission. Bioremediation of environmental pollutants can be achieved under denitrifying

condition which is an important sight of denitrification process [10]. Although the genes encoding the denitrifying reductases have been studied in only few species but the denitrifying ability has been found in microorganism belonging to numerous group of bacteria [11] and Archaea [12]. Boz *et al.* [13] reported that denitrification activity depend on abundance of bacteria in the soil. So, it is necessary the quantification of denitrifying bacteria for understanding the nitrogen cycle [14].

Pseudomonas chlororaphis subsp. *aureofaciens* [15] referring to the pigment producing, gram negative, motile, polar flagellated, rod bacterium, isolated from clay near the river mass [16]. The 16s rRNA analysis includes this bacteria into the *p. chlororaphis* group [17]. This species generally found in the rhizosphere and also in the adjacent sediments [18]. *P. chlororaphis* are potential denitrifiers because the end product of denitrification by *P. chlororaphis* tends to be N_2O [19]. *P. chlororaphis* have biogeochemical importance for producing dinitrogen gas from nitrate [17] due to their ability

to perform denitrification. *P. chlororaphis* have become more valuable organism of interest for agriculture due to the effectiveness as a bio-control agent [20]. Raio *et al.* [21] mentioned that, *P. chlororaphis* subsp. *aureofaciens* strain show its highest efficacy against a forest plant pathogen.

As a matter of fact denitrifiers are more numerous than any other functional groups involved in the nitrogen (N₂) cycle reported to comprise up to 5 percent of all soil bacteria. The two types of functionally equivalent but alternative genes for nitrite reductase have been identified in denitrifying bacteria: a copper containing nitrite reductase (CuNiR) *NirK* gene (E.C. 1.7.99.3) and cytochrome cd₁ *NirS* nitrite reductase (E.C. 1.7.2.1) [22, 23]. CuNiR are divided into two subclasses based on their colors, blue and green, and their redox partners, azurin and pseudoazurin, respectively. Both subclasses show a trimeric structure. The *NirK* gene catalyzes the reduction of nitrite (NO₂) to nitric oxide (NO) in the denitrification process and is responsible for the loss of terrestrial nitrogen to the atmosphere [24]. It has comprehensibly been used in recent years to lucid the composition of the denitrifier community and diversity in water columns of fresh water and sea water [1, 25]. Clark *et al.* [4] noticed that bacteria containing *NirK* are most probably responsible for the increased denitrification potential associated with organic carbon and nitrogen in the soil. Attard *et al.* [26] reported that although *NirK* and *NirS* gene copy number were similar in the soils at two different study sites, the observed changes in potential denitrification were significantly correlated to the changes in *NirK* gene copy number. Nitrite reductase has commonly been used as a molecular marker of denitrifying bacteria due to its rate limiting step from nitrite reduction to nitric oxide [27]. It has also been successfully detected by direct polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification with gene specific primers and gene probe analysis [28].

The research into protein structure and function from the sequence of CuNiR encoding *NirK* genes are limited in Bangladesh and even other country of the world. To our knowledge the three dimensional structure of CuNiR of *P. chlororaphis* subsp. *aureofaciens* is unavailable in Protein Data Bank (PDB) (www.rcsb.org) and also in the PMDB database. Therefore, it is very interesting as well as important to carry out the study of CuNiR of our selected microorganism. Therefore, the objectives of this study were to analyze the amino acid sequence of CuNiR and also the prediction of the 3D structure and function through several bioinformatics tools and servers. The results of this work will be valuable to the researcher to understand the properties, structure and function of CuNiR in future.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Retrieval of target and template sequence

The 363 amino acid residues containing sequence of *P. chlororaphis* subsp. *aureofaciens* *NirK* gene encoding CuNiR was retrieved in Fasta format from NCBI Gene Bank Database (Gene Bank ID : CAA79939.1). The templates were selected from Swiss-Model [29] Template Library (SMTL). The homologous crystallographic protein model was selected as template based on query coverage, lower resolution, lowest e-

value and 70% above sequence identity. The template identification is also confirmed by the Predictprotein server [30].

Primary structure analysis using Bioinformatics servers

The physico-chemical properties were predicted using the ExPasy ProtParam server. This server showed various important protein properties including molecular weight, Pⁱ value, and extinction coefficient (EC), instability index (II), aliphatic index (AI), negatively and positively charged residues, and also grand average hydropathy (GRAVY) value. The PSIPRED server [31] was used to predict the secondary structural features of the protein. Generally most of the protein contains the disordered regions and these regions of CuNiR protein were anticipated through the GlobPlot v2.3 server [32]. The subcellular localization of protein was predicted by both CELLO2GO [33] and Psortb v3.0.2 [34] server. The BindN+ server (<http://bioinfo.ggc.org/bindn+/>) with default parameters was used to find out the important DNA and RNA binding residues from the CuNiR protein sequence [35].

Homology modeling of CuNiR protein

Homology modeling was done using Modeller 9v14 [36] which is a computer program that models three dimensional structures of proteins and their assemblies by satisfaction of spatial restraints. The program requires one sequence of known 3D structure and python 2.3 script files containing modeler commands. The co-ordinate file of templates from PDB was also used for protein modeling. Modeller 9v14 was used to generate the desired models of this target and the generated models were visualized with PyMOL v1.3 software.

Model refinement, evaluation and submission to PMDB database

The predicted protein model which contains lowest DOPE (Low Discrete Optimized Protein Energy) score was subjected to energy minimization using Swiss-PdbViewer version 4.1.0 with a harmonic constraint of 100 kJ/mol/Å². It was applied for all protein atoms, using the steepest descent and conjugate gradient technique to eliminate the bad contacts between protein atoms and structural water molecules. Computations were carried out in vacuo with the GROMOS96 43B1 parameters set [37]. The stereochemical quality and accuracy of the model was evaluated with PROCHECK [38] by Ramachandran plot analysis [39]. Z-score was calculated using interactive ProSA web server [40]. QMEAN server [41] and Verify 3D [42] were also used to evaluate the model and the evaluated protein model was submitted to PMDB (Protein Model Database) database [43].

Characterization of the modeled structure

The secondary structural motifs were used to characterize the modeled protein structure. The modeled structure was analyzed using PDBsum server (<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbsum/>) [44] for the prediction of secondary structural motifs, clefts and pores information. The ligand binding sites, active sites and also the functions were predicted using the COFACTOR server [45].

The secondary structural features help to identify the location and amount of alpha helix, extended strand and random coils in the protein three dimensional structures. In that case, the target and template sequences were submitted to the PSIPRED server to know the secondary structural features of CuNiR protein. The result showed that the target sequence contain 11.57% (42 residues) alpha helix, 28.37% (103 residues) extended strand and 60.06% (218 residues) random coils whereas the template sequence (1NDS_A) contain 9.09% (30 residues), 30.61% (101 residues) and 60.30% (199 residues) alpha helix, extended strand and random coils, respectively. So, the results indicate the close relationship between the target and template sequences. The CELLO2GO and Psortb v3.0.2 server showed the subcellular location of our selected CuNiR protein is periplasm with significant score (Figure. 2).

Figure 2: The subcellular localization of the *P. chlororaphis* subsp. *aureofaciens* CuNiR protein.

The disordered or unstructured regions can play a significant role in the catalytic activity of the protein which was predicted by the GlobPlot server. The disordered regions are shown in three-dimensional structures as Figure 3.

Figure 3: Disorder regions of the *P. chlororaphis* subsp. *aureofaciens* CuNiR protein.

The non-globular unstructured regions usually cover short linear peptide motifs which are essential for protein functions. The amino acid residues namely Ala, Arg, Gly, Lys, Gln, Glu, Ser and Pro are responsible for creating the intrinsic disordered regions in the protein sequence whereas the Ile, Leu, Val, Phe, Tyr and Trp reduce the intrinsically disordered

regions of a protein [49, 50]. The plot depicts six disordered regions in the amino acid sequence of CuNiR and among these disordered regions the sixth disordered region is long with 15 amino acid residues and then the third disordered region with 9 amino acid residues (Table 2).

Table 2: The disordered sequences and their positions in the CuNiR protein sequence

Disordered regions	Disordered sequence	positions
1.	PHEQV	45-49
2.	AMTFNGSMPGPTLV	79-92
3.	ATNSMPHNVDHFH	107-118
4.	LPRDGLRDPQ	175-184
5.	YIPKDKDGHYKDYDPD	202-216
6.	DSRPHLIGGHGDWVWTTGKFANPPQRNMTW	269-299

The predicted disordered regions contain Ala, Pro, Gly, Arg, and Ser and also contain the disordered region reducing amino acid residues in the CuNiR protein sequence. The proteins do not contain the disordered regions in the same position of amino acid residues such as the disordered regions in Fructose Biphosphate Aldolase of *staphylococcus aureus* [51]. So, the results revealed that the protein contains the disordered region forming and disordered region reducing amino acid residues at the same sequence and as a result the disordered regions are not harmful for the proteins. The selected CuNiR protein also contained the globular region and is found in 2-78 and 93-201 amino acid positions and these regions perhaps work as the domains of the protein. The ProDom web tool was used for the verification of these globular regions and the server predicted 12 domain positions in the amino acid sequence and among these positions 9 domain regions were located at the same positions which were predicted by the GlobPlot server.

BindN+ server was used to analyze and predict the DNA and RNA binding residues from amino acid sequence. According to Wang et al. [35], BindN+ applies support vector machines (SVMs) to sequence based prediction of DNA or RNA-binding residues from biochemical features and evolutionary information. It has also mentioned that, in BindN+ server, the prediction accuracy for DNA binding from cross-validation is about 79% with equal sensitivity and specificity and for RNA binding residues, the estimated accuracy is over 75%.

DNA-binding residues in protein sequence have distinct biophysical characteristics and it controls the vital biological processes of protein-DNA interactions [52]. DNA-binding residues recognition in protein sequence is important for understanding the mechanism of DNA-protein interactions [53], gene expression and for guiding site-directed mutagenesis [54]. Therefore, the opportunity for recognition of DNA-binding residues has enhanced more attention of the scientists and has become a central theme in research related to the function of protein. Result showed that residues S2, R5, S6, P106, S110, T121, R141, R146, G304, S305, A306 and Y319 were present at the binding site of DNA in protein with different confidence level (Table 3).

Table 3: DNA and RNA binding residues of the *P. chlororaphis* subsp. *aureofaciens* CuNiR protein molecule.

S.N.	RNA Binding sites			DNA Binding sites		
	Residue Position	Residue Name	Confidence Level	Residue Position	Residue Name	Confidence Level
1.	2	Ser (S)	0.3927	2	Ser (S)	0.3382
2.	77	Leu (L)	0.3704	5	Arg (R)	0.3456
3.	105	Asn (N)	0.3920	6	Ser (S)	0.4323
4.	106	Pro (P)	0.3794	106	Pro (P)	0.3272
5.	113	His (H)	0.6628	110	Ser (S)	0.3779
6.	114	Asn (N)	0.6213	121	Thr (T)	0.2876
7.	116	Asp (D)	0.4223	141	Arg (R)	0.3438
8.	136	Gln (Q)	0.4266	146	Arg (R)	0.3336
9.	137	Glu (E)	0.4821	304	Gly (G)	0.2737
10.	159	Met (M)	0.4000	305	Ser (S)	0.5244
11.	169	Asn (N)	0.7053	306	Ala (A)	0.3244
12.	173	Met (M)	0.3648	319	Tyr (Y)	0.5281
13.	177	Arg (R)	0.3751			
14.	239	Asn (N)	0.4027			
15.	302	Pro (P)	0.3658			
16.	305	Ser (S)	0.3757			
17.	363	Gln (Q)	0.3605			

Interaction between protein and RNA play essential roles in variety of biological process such as messenger RNA stability, protein synthesis [55], localization and translation [56], splicing, polyadenylation [57], and post-transcriptional regulation [58]. Therefore, RNA-binding residues recognition in protein sequence is important for understanding of protein function. Result showed that the residues S2, L77, N105, P106, H113, N114, D116, Q136, E137, M159, N169, M173, R177, N239, P302, S305 and Q363 were present at the binding site of RNA in protein with confidence level 0.3605- 0.7053 (Table 3). The result also shows that residues S2, P106 and S305 were present at the binding site of both DNA and RNA in protein molecule.

Molecular homology modeling, energy minimization and evaluation

The protein sequence of CuNiR having accession id CAA79939 has no three dimensional structure present in the Protein Data Bank (PDB). Therefore, the template PDB id: 1NDS_A were identified by the Swiss-model template library against the Protein Data Bank (PDB). The three dimensional structure of the CuNiR protein was modeled by using the Modeller 9v14 program and the best model was selected among from all the predicted model based on the lowest DOPE score. Then modeled protein with low DOPE score was subjected for energy minimization with Swiss-PdbViewer software. The total force field energy of the protein model was 26833.357 kJ/ mole but after the energy minimization the value came down to -12734.138 kJ/mole. Further evaluation program, PROCHECK was used to perform full geometric analysis as well as stereochemical quality of a protein structure by analyzing residue geometry and overall structural geometry. The Ramachandran Plot statistics result showed 93.0% residues in most favored region, 5.0% residues in the

additional allowed region, 1.0% in the generously allowed region and 1.0% of the residues in the disallowed region (Figure 4) whereas the template model (1NDS) contain 0.0% residues in most favored region, 0.0% residues in the additional allowed region, 0.0% in the generously allowed region and 100.0% of the residues in the disallowed region.

Figure 4: Ramachandran plot of the predicted model. Here out of total 363 residues present in the model, 278(93%) lies in most favored regions, 15(5.0%) in additional allowed regions, 3 (1.0%) in generously allowed regions and 3(1.0%) in disallowed regions. Here, 2 end-residues (excl. Gly and Pro), 37 residues and 25 Proline residues.

The results revealed that there are significant difference exist between the target and template model but our predicted protein model is more acceptable according to the result of Ramachandran Plot statistics. The QMEAN (Qualitative Model Energy Analysis) score is a multiple scoring function that estimates the global quality of the models. The score reflects the anticipated global model reliability ranges from 0 to 1. The QMEAN score of the model was predicted as 0.667(Z score - 1.1) which indicates good quality of the model. Verify 3D structure evaluation server analyzes the compatibility of an atomic model (3D) with its own amino acid sequence (1D). Eisenberg et al. [42]analyzed that the profile score above zero in verify 3D graph corresponds to acceptable environment of the model. In this study the predicted high score of 0.67 indicates that environmental profile of the model is good quality. After analyzing the Verify 3D data, 273 (75.21%) of 363 residues in the model were found to have score above 0.2 that also indicate the good quality of the protein model. ProSA was used to check the potential errors of the protein 3D model. The positive Z-score expose the bad quality whereas the negative value indicate the good quality of the model. In this study, the Z-score of the protein model was negative -6.68 (Figure 5) but the Z-score of the template model was negative -5.82 in the NMR region which designating the acceptability of the modeled protein. After completing the evaluation process the protein model was submitted to the PMDB database and assigned a unique identifying number PM0080184. The visualization and analyses of the predicted CuNiR protein was performed through the PyMOL software (Figure 6a).

Figure 5: ProSA-web server analysis of CuNiR. ProSA web z-score of CuNiR is highlighted as large dot.

Analysis of the modeled CuNiR protein structure

The homology or comparative protein model prediction methods have created the opportunity for the further research on the protein structure. The protein structure prediction through NMR or x-ray crystallographic technology is very expensive, time consuming and also quite challenging work. So, the homology model helps to further research and also helps to know the information about clefts, pores, ligand binding sites, active sites, docking, and the function of the respective protein within very short time in comparison with the NMR or x-ray crystallographic protein model.

In this study, the predicted protein model was characterized by the PDBsum server and this server showed the results on secondary structural motifs or promotifs, clefts, and pores of the protein structure. The *P. chlororaphis* subsp. *aureofaciens* CuNiR protein contain 6 sheets, 6 beta hairpins, 8 beta bulges, 23 strands, 5 helices, 41 beta turns, 4 gamma turns and 1 helix-helix interaction as the secondary structural motifs. The helix- helix interaction occurred between the helix-3 and helix-5 and the distance and angle between two helices were 10.8Å and 96.3°, respectively. The protein model contain about 10 clefts and the first four clefts volume were 4613.20, 1329.33, 1202.77, and 741.66 and these clefts consist of positive (H, K, R), negative (D, E), neutral (S, T, N, Q), aliphatic (A, V, L, I, M), aromatic (F, W, Y) and proline and glycine residues. The average depth of these four clefts was 17.07, 14.90, 9.30 and 8.42, respectively. The protein structure also contain the pores which are connected internal spaces going through the structure. Our modeled protein structure contains only one pores and it is longer than 25Å. The radius and length of the protein model was 1.13 and 119.7 whereas free R, Hpathy, Hphob and polarity value was 1.45, -0.88, -0.02 and 20.1, respectively. The pore contains positive (H, K, R), negative (D, E), neutral (S, T, N, Q), aliphatic (A, V, L, I, M), and aromatic (F, W, Y) residues but no proline or glycine residues were existed like clefts.

The online COFACTOR server was used for the identification of enzyme classification (EC), ligand binding sites and also for the consensus prediction of the gene ontology (GO) terms. The server identified the CuNiR protein with the enzyme classification EC 1.7.2.1 and anticipated that amino acid residues Val151, Val165, Ser167, Gly170, Thr195, Gly197, Ser199, Leu201, Pro233, Phe238, Ser264, Ala266, Arg268, Ser270, Pro272, Ile300, Pro302, Ser305, Leu322, Asn325 and Glu328 can play significant role in the catalytic reaction. The C-score, TM-score and identity of the first hit was 0.644, 0.884 and 0.870, respectively and all the other PDB hit showed the same EC number (Table 4).

Table 4: Top 5 enzyme homologs in PDB by COFACTOR.

Rank	C-score	PDB Hit	TM-score	RMSD	IDEN	Cov.	EC number	Predicted active site residues
1	0.644	1ndrB	0.884	1.17	0.870	0.901	1.7.2.1	151,165,167,170,195,197,199,201,233,238,264,266,268,270,272,300,302,305,322,325,328
2	0.563	1et7A	0.885	1.59	0.634	0.909	1.7.2.1	82,84,116,163
3	0.530	1kbvA	0.786	1.84	0.353	0.826	1.7.2.1	82,84,116,163,273
4	0.477	1kbwD	0.785	1.75	0.353	0.824	1.7.2.1	273,302,324
5	0.398	2zooA	0.784	2.10	0.332	0.832	1.7.2.1	116,153,154,155,163

The server was also used to find out the similar binding sites for the comparison of the consensus binding sites with predicted ligand binding sites. The server predicted six PDB hits namely 1ndrA, 1zdqA, 1zdqA, 2xwzB, 2e86A and 2e86B

and among all these hits the 1ndrA contains **Cu** as a ligand with significant C-score (0.81) and TM-score (0.884) (Table 5).

Table 5: Template proteins with similar binding sites searched by COFACTOR.

Rank	C-score	PDB Hit	TM-score	RMSD	IDEN	Cov.	BS-score	Ligand Name	Predicted binding site residues
1	0.81	1ndrA	0.884	1.17	0.870	0.901	1.56	CU	113,154,163,168
2	0.59	1zdqA	0.884	1.69	0.642	0.912	1.69	MSM	78,80,111,113,162,163
3	0.42	1gs6X	0.885	1.34	0.777	0.904	1.83	MG	284,285,301,302,305
4	0.41	2xwzB	0.882	1.23	0.782	0.901	1.58	NO	273,275,324
5	0.37	2e86A	0.886	1.80	0.643	0.915	1.74	AZI	273,275,324
6	0.37	2e86B	0.882	1.66	0.641	0.909	1.76	AZI	116,153,160

The COFACTOR server showed the ligand binding residues and the residues were His113, Cys154, His163 and Met168 and it has shown in Figure 6b. We used the PDBsum server for the verification of this metal binding sites but this server showed only the Cys154 residue as ligand binding site with 1 hydrogen bond and 14 non-bonded contacts. The hydrogen bond was formed between the atom number 1370 and 1165 with the atom SG and the distance between these 2 atoms was 2.22 Å. The non-bonded contacts involved Met80, His113 and His163, Cys154, Pro156 and Met168 with different distance. The previous study showed that type I copper atoms is buried

within the proteins N-terminal domain and each one is synchronized by His, Cys and Met residues [59, 60]. In this study, it has also been demonstrated that the Met, His, and Cys residues are involved in the Cu binding site and it ensures the potentiality of the predicted protein model. The COFACTOR server predicted the copper ion binding activity (interacting selectively and non-covalently with copper ions), and nitrite reductase (NO-forming) activity as the molecular function and also some biological and cellular function with significant GO-score (Table 6). The predicted functions are highly associated with the CuNiR enzyme.

Figure 6: (a) the three dimensional structure of the *P. chlororaphis* subsp. *aureofaciens* CuNiR protein. (b) the ligand (CU) binding sites of the CuNiR protein.

Table 6: Consensus prediction of gene ontology terms searched by COFACTOR.

Serial No.	GO Term	Description	GO-score
1	GO:0005507	copper ion binding	0.99
2	GO:0050421	nitrite reductase (NO-forming) activity	0.99
3	GO:0055114	oxidation-reduction process	0.99
4	GO:0042128	nitrate assimilation	0.98
5	GO:0042597	periplasmic space	0.98

CONCLUSION

The sequence of *P. chlororaphis* subsp. *Aureofaciens* NirK gene encoding CuNiR is chosen for this study as because very little *in silico* information is present currently. In this study, homology modeling and comparative proteomics approach have been used to propose the well- defined 3D structure, ligand binding sites and functions that will help to understand the biological roles of the protein. The DNA and RNA binding sites play an essential roles in the protein function and the predicted result showed that residues S2, P106 and S305 were present at the binding site of both DNA and RNA in protein molecule and these residues may be the future research prospect. So, it can be concluded that the developed protein homology model and the structural characteristics of this protein will help to initiate the research on molecular mechanism of denitrification but the experimental verification and application are needed to be sure about these findings and we have intended to do it.

COMPETING INTEREST

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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